

Perylenediimide-Incorporated Covalent Triazine Framework: A Highly Conductive Carbon Support for Copper Single-Atom Catalyst in Electrocatalytic CO₂ Conversion

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ABSTRACT: Here, we show that a perylenediimide-incorporated covalent triazine framework (PDI-CTF) leads to adequate conductive carbon support for copper single-atom catalysts (Cu-SACs), allowing the selective CO₂ electroreduction to methanol. CTF-Cu-SACs converted CO₂ into methanol with a faradaic efficiency of 72.6% at a low overpotential (0.2 V vs. RHE). While increasing the overpotential (0.2 to -0.4 V vs. RHE), CTF-Cu-SACs promoted syngas (CO and H₂) production with faradaic efficiencies of 53.2% and 39.5 %, respectively. Moreover, CTF-Cu-SACs led to robust catalytic stability for 20 h of continuous electrolysis in an aqueous solution. Notably, it was observed that additional nitrogen doping to the PDI-CTF profoundly

influences product selectivity, possibly due to the synergetic effect of highly conductive pyrolyzed CTF and N-chelating ligands with rich active sites. Our results indicate that the PDI-CTF-based Cu-SACs provide abundant active sites for CO₂ adsorption, thus enhancing intermolecular ion and charge transportation that efficiently reduces CO₂ into methanol in an aqueous system.

Keywords: Perylenediimide, covalent triazine framework, copper, single-atom catalysts, CO₂ electroreduction, methanol

INTRODUCTION

Carbon dioxide (CO₂) accumulation in the atmosphere is a critical factor for global warming, becoming a major environmental threat.¹ Alleviating CO₂ emissions and tackling climate change risk is an urgent need. Conversion of CO₂ into value-added products using renewable energy sources *via* modern approaches is a promising strategy to address this issue.²⁻⁴ Electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction reactions (CO₂RR) have gained remarkable attention in heterogeneous catalysis due to their cost-effectiveness, eco-friendliness, and energy-efficient features.⁵⁻⁷ CO₂RR yields various hydrocarbons and fuels, including CO, CH₄, CH₃OH, CO, HCOOH (C₁ products), acetic acid, ethylene, ethanol, and propanol (C₂ or C₂₊ products).⁸ Product selectivity is still an issue, including the competition against hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). Thus, it is necessary to develop affordable catalysts that suppress HER and drive the CO₂RR efficiently at low overpotential with high product selectivity. However, C₁ products are preferred over C₂ or C₂₊ compounds in most of the CO₂RR since the latter need to overcome a high activation energy barrier.⁹ Methanol, in particular, is a crucial C₁ compound used as the primary precursor for producing bulk chemicals, including silicone and plastics.¹⁰ Yet, the electrochemical conversion of CO₂ into methanol with high efficiency and selectivity is limited, demanding more investigation into new classes of catalysts.^{10, 11}

Single-atom catalysts (SACs)¹²⁻¹⁶ are a novel class of emerging catalytic materials. Various nanostructured materials, including graphene,^{17,18} metal-organic frameworks (MOFs)¹⁹⁻²¹ carbon nanotube (CNT)^{22, 23}, and covalent organic frameworks (COFs)²⁴⁻²⁶ have been exploited as the carbon support for synthesizing SACs. The carbon support provides a unique electronic structure along with high conductivity.²⁷ Recently, we demonstrated Cu and Fe-based SACs using crystalline carbon nitride (PHI) as carbon support by the cation-exchange method. Under mild conditions, via photocatalysis, PHI-derived Cu-SACs and Fe-SACs showed remarkable catalytic activity for methane oxidation to methanol (2900 μmol g⁻¹) and

C-H bond oxidation reactions.^{28, 29} Due to their high unsaturated coordination, maximum atom utilization, distinctive electronic structure, and capacity to suppress HER, they have drawn expressive attention in CO₂RR.³⁰ Covalent triazine frameworks (CTFs),³¹ of the typical COF³² family, composed of strong covalent bonds, are another potential catalyst-supporting materials with similar properties.³³ Unlike MOFs, CTFs and COFs can be synthesized with various heteroatoms (i.e., N, S, etc.) and conductive features. For example, Perylenediimide³⁴⁻³⁶ (PDI)-incorporated CTF framework can provide high conductive and unique electronic properties for the whole system. Only a few attempts have been made to integrate PDI in the CTF^{37, 38} and no reports have shown the significance of such frameworks in CO₂RR.

Despite the significant advancements in developing various photo and electrocatalysts for CO₂RR,³⁹⁻⁵⁰ SACs based on COFs and CTFs are scarce in the literature.^{24, 51-53} Moreover, the production of methanol with high selectivity remains limited.^{10, 11} Copper-based (Cu-SACs), in particular, are promising for the electrocatalytic conversion of CO₂ into hydrocarbons and alcohols with high product selectivity in an aqueous solution.⁵⁴⁻⁶³ Thus, herein, we report CTF-Cu-SACs using PDI incorporated CTF as the conductive carbon support for CO₂RR. The CTF-Cu-SACs demonstrated high catalytic efficiency of converting CO₂-to-methanol with FE of 72.6% at 0.2 V vs. RHE. While increasing the overpotential (0.0 V to -0.4V), CTF-Cu-SACs favored syngas (CO and H₂) production. The CTF-Cu-SACs maintained high stability for 24 hours of continuous electrolysis. From this investigation, CTF-Cu-SACs pave the way to utilize PDI-incorporated CTFs as the sustainable conductive carbon support for next-generation SACs to be explored as potential electrocatalysts for CO₂RR by considering their structural designability for metal coordination and unique electronic features.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Synthesis of PDI-CTF

The PDI-CTF was prepared according to the literature.³⁷ Briefly, melamine (5 mM) was mixed with 3,4,9,10-perylenetetracarboxylic acid anhydride (PTCDA, 5 mM). The resulting mixture was then ground in an agate mortar for 30 minutes. Following this, the resultant mixture was carefully transferred into an alumina crucible and exposed to a calcination process at a temperature of 325 °C for 4 hours. This process occurred in an air atmosphere, with a controlled heating rate of 5 °C per minute. Ultimately, the resulting particles were collected for subsequent usage.

Synthesis of CTF-derived Cu-SACs (CTF-Cu-SACs)

In a typical synthesis, PDI-CTF (0.3g) and $\text{Cu}(\text{OAC})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.03g; 10 wt%) were grounded in a silica mortar for 30 min to attain a homogeneous mixture. Subsequently, the mixture was annealed at 900 °C, 3 °C/min, for 4 h under N_2 . After pyrolysis, the mixture was successfully leached at HCl (1M) and HNO_3 (1M) at 80 °C for 12 h each to remove metal nanoparticles or clusters, if any. Finally, the acid mixture was centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 10 min and thoroughly washed with water (MilliQ), followed by drying at 80 °C for 12 h under vacuum to obtain pure CTF-derived Cu-SACs (CTF-Cu-900). A similar strategy was used for synthesizing N-doped Cu-SACs (CTF-Cu-N-900) using melamine (1:10) as the nitrogen source. Metal-free pyrolyzed CTF (CTF-900) was also synthesized for comparison. The catalyst yield was calculated at ~ 55 to 66%.

Characterizations

A Shimadzu diffractometer (XRD-6000) with a Cu $K\alpha$ source ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) was used to record the results of a powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) investigation in the 10 ° to 80 ° (1 ° min^{-1}) range. All samples underwent thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) using a TGA Q500 analyzer in a platinum pan with airflow rates of 40 mL min^{-1} for the sample and 60 mL min^{-1} for the reference, respectively. The temperature was raised at a rate of 10 °C per minute. Micromeritics equipment (ASAP 2020) was used to analyze the adsorption and desorption of nitrogen at 80 °C for one hour. It was done using the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) equation to determine the specific surface area (SSA). A confocal LabRAM micro-Raman system with a 532 nm laser was used to perform Raman spectroscopy. A high-performance EA 125 hemispherical analyzer was used for the XPS analysis, and an operating pressure of 2×10^{-9} mbar was used in the ultra-high vacuum chamber. The samples were exposed to monochromatic Al K radiation ($h\nu = 1486.6 \text{ eV}$). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) were carried out using a JEOL JEM 2010 microscope with a tungsten filament. The samples were deposited using carbon tape before analysis. Using an FEI JEOL-7800F, field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) was carried out. An FEI-TECNAI G2 F20 microscope was used to record the high-angle annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscopy (HAADF-STEM) and element mapping analysis (EDS) (200 kV). On an electrochemical workstation, LSV was captured (Autolab PGSTAT30, Metrohm). Liquid products were examined by ^1H NMR spectroscopy (600 MHz, AscendTM 600 Bruker) at 25 °C. The standard and reference combined D_2O containing dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO; 5.0 mM) and TSPd4 (0.22 mM). For the ^1H NMR, the sample (540 μL) and the solution mentioned above (60 μL each) were combined. The ^1H NMR data were quantified using the MestReNova

program. Gas chromatography (GC Thermo CP-3800) was employed to find gaseous products. A carboxen 1010 plot capillary GC column (30 m × 0.32 mm, average thickness 15 μm) was used to separate the gaseous products of the CO₂ reduction on the GC instrument equipped with flame ionization (FID) and thermal conductivity (TCD) detectors and methanizer. Argon was used as the carrier gas.

Electrochemical measurements

The electrochemical measurements were performed in a gas-tight H-type electrochemical cell equipped with a three-electrode system. All the measurements were done at an ambient temperature. Nafion membrane was used to separate the anodic and cathodic compartments. Carbon paper (CP), platinum grid (Pt), and Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) were used as the working (WE), counter (CE), and reference (RE) electrodes, respectively. All the applied potentials were converted into RHE using the equation $E_{\text{RHE}} = E_{(\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl})} + E^{\circ}_{(\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl})} + (0.0591 \times \text{pH})$.

Linear Sweep Voltammetry (LSV): LSV was performed in the potential window of 0 to -1.4 V vs. Ag/AgCl (3M) at a scan rate of 25 mV s⁻¹ using 0.5 M KOH as an aqueous electrolyte. Before the measurement, N₂ (99.999%) or CO₂ (99.999%) were purged to saturate the 0.5 M KOH for 10 min by maintaining a flow of CO₂ throughout the measurement.

Catalyst preparation: The pyrolyzed CTFs (CTF-900, CTF-Cu-900, and CTF-Cu-N-900) (2.0 mg) were dispersed in isopropanol (500 L), MilliQ water (500 L), and Nafion (5%) (5.6 L) to create the catalytic ink. For even dispersion, the mixes were sonicated for 20 min. After that, the CP (1x1 cm²) was spray-coated with the catalytic ink, which was then dried for 12 hours at room temperature.

Chronoamperometry (CA): To assess electrochemical CO₂RR, CA was used. The cathodic compartment was initially purged with high-purity CO₂ (99.99%) for around 15 minutes. The CO₂RR was then performed for 30 minutes in a CO₂ environment. Following the process, the gaseous and liquid byproducts underwent GC and NMR spectroscopic analyses, respectively. All of the products' FEs were estimated using the equation given in the literature.³

Electrochemical surface area (ECSA): ECSA was measured using cyclic voltammetry (CV) at the solid-liquid interface by measuring double-layer capacitance. The measurement was carried out in a non-faradaic potential range of 0.0 to 0.5 V vs. Ag/AgCl (3M) at the scan rates ranging from 10 to 50 mV s⁻¹ to construct a plot of the charging current density differences against the scan rate at a fixed potential of 0.25 V. ECSA was carried out according to the literature.^{3, 64}

Electrical impedance spectroscopy (EIS): Glassy carbon, platinum, and Ag/AgCl were used as the working, counter, and reference electrodes, respectively, to record EIS on an Autolab

(PGSTAT302N). The settings for all of the analyses were CO₂-saturated. All the catalysts had a frequency range of 0.001-10⁵ Hz and an amplitude of 0.005 V.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthesis and characterization

As depicted in Figure 1, the CTF-Cu-SACs (CTF-Cu-900 and CTF-Cu-N-900) were synthesized using PDI-CTF as the conductive carbon support. CTF-Cu-900 was produced by pyrolyzing PDI-CTF³⁷ in the presence of Cu(OAc)₂·2H₂O at 900 °C for 4 hours at a heating rate of 3 °C/min in an N₂ environment. CTF-Cu-SACs with additional N-doping (CTF-Cu-N-900) were synthesized using melamine as the N-donating agent. Notably, N-doping on carbonaceous frameworks increases the stability of Cu atoms by preventing their aggregation with surrounding atoms.¹⁹ We also synthesized the metal-free carbon substrate CTF-900 for comparison in the absence of Cu(OAc)₂·H₂O. Following pyrolysis, all samples were treated for 12 hours at 80 °C with 1 M HCl and 1 M HNO₃ to remove Cu nanoparticles (CuNPs) or clusters adsorbed on the framework's edge.¹⁹

Fig. 1 - Schematic illustration for the synthesis of Cu-SACs on PDI-CTF support.

XRD profile of CTF-900, CTF-Cu-900, and CTF-Cu-N-900 exhibited a broad peak at 26.4° and 44.1°, attributed to the plane (002) and (100) of the graphitic structure.^{11, 13} Bare PDI-CTF

shows clear crystalline diffraction peaks (Fig. 2a). With CTF-Cu-900 and CTF-Cu-N-900, no apparent crystalline peaks were seen, indicating the absence of any metal nanoparticles or clusters.^{11, 13} TGA analysis was used to determine the thermal characteristics of CTF-900, CTF-Cu-900, and CTF-Cu-N-900 (Fig. 2b). The weight loss for CTF-Cu-900 and CTF-Cu-N-900 was 98.7% and 97.5%, respectively, at the highest temperature (800 °C). However, when the maximum temperature was applied, the metal-free CTF-900 catalyst lost utterly (100%) weight. The catalysts' negligible weight loss compared to the metal-free CTF-900 catalyst confirms the evidence that metal atoms are present in CTF-Cu-900 and CTF-Cu-N-900. Of all the samples examined, CTF-Cu-N-900 had the lowest weight loss (97.5%), which could be attributed to the additional N doping increasing the amount of Cu-coordinated with N-ligand in the carbon matrix.

The surface area and pore volume of CO₂RR are considered crucial attributes as they enhance its catalytic activity by providing a more significant number of catalytic sites. The catalysts CTF-900 and CTF-Cu-900 yielded BET surface areas of about 13.7 m²/g and 8.9 m²/g, respectively, as shown in Figures S1a and S1b. Additionally, it was determined that the pore volumes of CTF-900 and CTF-Cu-900 were about 0.04 cm³/g and 0.05 cm³/g, respectively, as seen in Figures S1a and S1b. On the other hand, it was observed that the N-doped CTF-Cu-N-900 exhibited the highest BET surface area and pore volume among the samples, with values of around 99.8689 m²/g and 0.42 cm³/g, respectively (Fig. 2c and inset). It suggests that the metal atom experiences stabilization while the N-dopants contribute to an enlargement in the surface area.

Moreover, Raman spectra were performed to clarify the structure of CTF-Cu-SACs, which may be deconvoluted into four distinct peaks (Fig. 2d and S2). For instance, CTF-Cu-N-900 (Fig. 2d) showed peaks at around 1244 cm⁻¹ and 1350 cm⁻¹ attributed to the sp³ phase of a polyene-like structure (D4-band) and the carbon matrix. A band around 1524 cm⁻¹ may be related to the carbon matrix's Cu-N_x coordination or the amorphous sp² phase (D3 band). The in-plane vibration of the carbon atoms in the sp² electronic arrangement is attributed to a band at about 1604 cm⁻¹.¹⁹

Fig. 2 - Characterization of CTF-Cu-SACs. (a) Representative XRD profile of CTF, CTF-900, CTF-Cu-900, and CTF-Cu-N-900. (b) TGA profile of CTF-900, CTF-Cu-900, and CTF-Cu-N-900. (c) N₂ adsorption and desorption isotherm of CTF-Cu-N-900. Inset: Pore size distribution of CTF-Cu-N-900. (d) Raman spectrum of CTF-Cu-N-900.

The chemical composition of CTF-900, CTF-Cu-900, and CTF-Cu-N-900 is revealed by XPS analysis. The prominent peaks in the XPS survey spectra of CTF-Cu-900 and CTF-Cu-N-900 were carbon (C1s), nitrogen (N1s), and oxygen (O1s), respectively, at 284.8, 400 eV, and 530.6 eV. (Fig. S3a-c). The coordination of H₂O and O₂ with Cu single atoms to achieve a whole coordination sphere is likely the cause of oxygen's presence in CTF-Cu-SACs.⁶⁵ The presence of Cu2p with mixed valence states like Cu(I) (932.4 and 952.1 eV) and Cu(II) (934.9 and 954.8 eV) as well as the satellite peaks in the range of 942 to 948 eV, which could be attributed to the Cu-N_x coordination of Cu(I) and Cu(II) valence states, was demonstrated in the high-resolution spectrum by CTF-Cu-N-900 and CTF-Cu-900 (Fig. 3a and 3c). It is in line with past reports on N-doped Cu-SACs in a positive way.^{19, 66-68} Moreover, due to peak intensity variation, N-doping to the CTF-Cu-SACs significantly affected the Cu(I) : Cu(II) proportion. Due to the high amount of N-source, N-doped CTF-Cu-N-900, for example, showed intense

peaks for the Cu (II) over Cu (I) state, indicating that the catalyst mainly comprises of Cu-N₄ valence states rather than Cu-N₂ valence states. In contrast, CTF-Cu-900 exhibited high intensity for the Cu(I) state, ascribed to the Cu-N₂ valence states. Six suitable peaks were deconvoluted from the high-resolution N1s spectra of CTF-Cu-N-900 and CTF-900 (Fig. 3b and 3d). Pyridinic-N and graphitic-N states are linked to 398.4 eV and 400.8 eV peaks.^{19, 66-68} Importantly, the Cu-N_x coordination in CTF-Cu-SACs may be attributed to a peak at 399.4 eV.^{19, 66-68} Moreover, negative-N and oxidized-N were seen at energies of 397.9 eV and 403–406 eV.²⁸ The catalyst CTF-Cu-N-900 displays a substantially higher N-peak than other catalysts, indicating that the N-atoms in the catalyst were added through additional N-doping (Fig. S3c). The survey spectrum of the metal-free CTF-900 verifies that there are no metal peaks, as expected (Fig. S3a). Our findings showed that the N and Cu atoms dominate the carbon matrix, suggesting their strong coordination in mixed valence states makes them a promising option for electrocatalysis.

Fig. 3 - Surface composition of CTF-Cu-SACs. XPS high-resolution Cu2p spectrum of CTF-Cu-N-900 (a) and CTF-Cu-900 (c). Respective XPS high-resolution N1s spectrum of CTF-Cu-N-900 (b) and CTF-Cu-900 (d).

CTF-900 and CTF-Cu-900 both exhibited a foam-like structure in field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) images (Fig. S4a and S4b), whereas CTF-Cu-N-900 was made of an ultrathin sheet-like structure (Fig. 4a). The carbon matrix contains atoms of carbon (C), nitrogen (N), oxygen (O), and copper (Cu), according to SEM-EDS elemental mapping (Fig. S5). CTF-Cu-N-900 was found to have a sheet-like structure in HAAD-STEM analysis (Fig. 4b). Remarkably, even at high magnification (Fig. 4b, S6a, and S6b), neither copper nanoparticles (CuNPs) nor clusters are seen in the HAAD-STEM pattern of CTF-Cu-N-900, suggesting the presence of copper single atoms.¹⁹ Moreover, the selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern only revealed the carbon diffraction fringe (Fig. 4b, inset). This observation agrees with the CTF-Cu-SACs' XRD pattern, with no distinctive peaks connected to CuNPs or clusters. HAAD-EDS mapping of the CTF-Cu-N-900 demonstrated the presence of extensively scattered copper single atoms in the carbon matrix (Fig. 4c and 4d). Also, the chosen region's HAAD-EDS graph amply supports the existence of the copper atom in CTF-Cu-N-900 (Fig. 4e and 4f).

Fig. 4 - Morphology of CTF-Cu-SACs. (a) FE-SEM patterns of CTF-Cu-N-900. (b) HAAD-STEM image of CTF-Cu-N-900 (inset shows the SAED pattern). (c and d) HAADF-STEM image and representative EDS mapping of CTF-Cu-N-900 (the white dot represents an isolated copper atom). (e and f) EDS graph from the selected region of CTF-Cu-N-900.

Electrochemical CO₂ conversion

The electrocatalytic CO₂RR performance of CTF-Cu-SACs was tested in a gas-tight H-type electrochemical cell with a three-electrode configuration, with 0.5 M KOH from 0.0 V to -1.4 V vs. Ag/AgCl under N₂ or CO₂-saturated circumstances. CTF-Cu-N-900 produced a higher current density (~11 mAcm⁻²) in linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) than the other catalysts (Fig. 5a). A significantly greater current density of CTF-Cu-N-900 under CO₂-saturated electrolytic conditions (Fig. 5b) than N₂-saturated conditions (Fig. 5b) suggests its superior catalytic performance in CO₂RR.²⁴ Also, the extra N-doping to the CTF-Cu-SACs demonstrated tremendous relevance in raising the current densities, a crucial aspect for electrocatalytic CO₂RR. N-doping into the carbon matrix creates additional defects to anchor single metal sites and tune the electrical structure of the entire system. Also, the low ohmic resistance of KOH, as an electrolyte, enhances the current density compared to the other electrolytes.⁶⁹

Fig. 5 - Electrochemical CO₂ conversion of CTF-Cu-SACs. (a) LSV curves were recorded in CO₂-saturated 0.5 M KOH solution of CTF-Cu-N-900, CTF-Cu-900, CTF-900, and reference electrodes. (b) LSV curves were recorded in N₂ and CO₂-saturated 0.5 M KOH solution of CTF-Cu-N-900. Faradaic efficiencies of all products at the potential range of 0.2V to -0.4V vs. RHE for CTF-900 (c), CTF-Cu-900 (d), and CTF-Cu-N-900 (e). (f) The stability of CTF-Cu-N-900 for 20 h at -0.8 V vs. Ag/AgCl (3M).

Methanol, acetic acid, acetate, and acetone were all detected in trace amounts in CO₂RR using the metal-free catalyst CTF-900 at the lower overpotential (0.2 V vs. RHE). However, at the upper range of overpotentials (0.0 to -0.4 V versus RHE), significant HER was noted (Fig. 5c). The primary products of the metal-doped catalysts CTF-Cu-900 and CTF-Cu-N-900, on the other hand, ranged from 0.2 V to -0.4 V vs. RHE and were methanol, CO, and H₂ (Fig. 5d and 5e). For instance, CTF-Cu-900 favored syngas generation with FE of 25.2% (CO) and 59.5% (H₂) at higher overpotential (-0.4 V vs. RHE) and CO₂ to methanol with FE of 22.6% at a lower overpotential (0.2 V vs. RHE). Notably, N-doped CTF-Cu-N-900 showed excellent catalytic performance in the conversion of CO₂ into methanol with FE of 72.6% at a relatively low overpotential of 0.2 V vs. RHE (Fig. 6a). The FE of methanol steadily dropped as the overpotential increased from 0.2 V to -0.4 V vs. RHE. Still, the FE of CO and H₂ dramatically increased, reaching their highest values of 53.2% and 39.5%, respectively, at -0.4 V vs. RHE (Fig. 6b). Besides, all the three catalysts yield acetic acid, acetate, acetone and methane as a trace amounts throughout the potential range (Fig. 5c-e). Moreover, a negligible formate production was observed only at higher over potential at -0.4 V (Fig. 5e). Overall, it shows that at 0.2 V vs. RHE, the N-doped CTF-Cu-N-900 produces the maximum FE of methanol (72.6%).

Fig. 6 - Faradaic efficiencies of methanol (a) and CO (b) at the potential range of 0.2 V to -0.4 V vs. RHE for CTF-SACs. (c) EIS spectra of CTF-SACs catalysts under CO₂-saturated conditions in the 0.001-10⁵ Hz frequency range with an AC amplitude of 0.005V. (d) ECSA of CTF-SACs under CO₂-saturated conditions from 10 to 50 mVs⁻¹.

As discussed in earlier reports, C₁ molecules (CO and formic acid) were the primary products during most of the CO₂RR using Cu-based M-N-C catalysts.⁵⁴⁻⁶³ CTF-Cu-SACs could convert CO₂ into methanol in an aqueous solution with an FE of 72.6% and a partial current density of ~ -11 mA.cm⁻². This catalytic performance of CTF-Cu-SACs is superior to the previously reported state-of-the-art catalysts based on Cu for CO₂ reduction to methanol in electrocatalysis (Table S1).

The proposed hypothesis posits that in the reaction pathway of CO₂RR, carbon monoxide (CO) serves as an intermediate species, facilitating the formation of C₁ or C₂₊ molecules by proton and electron transfer processes. The relatively low binding energy of *CO intermediates on the catalyst surface enhances the removal of CO as a product. At the same time, the firmly adsorbed *CO species undergo further reduction processes leading to the formation of methanol.¹¹ Also, it is worth noting that copper nanoparticles (CuNPs) or clusters can potentially promote the formation of multi-carbon (C₂ or C₂₊) products. It is due to the proximity of *CO intermediates, which enables C-C coupling within a carbonaceous matrix.⁵⁴

⁷⁰⁻⁷³ Nevertheless, it is widely observed that single-atom catalysts (SACs) tend to result in the formation of C₁ compounds. It might be attributed to the greater interatomic distance between the metal atoms, which hinders the interaction between carbon atoms (C-C interaction).⁵⁴⁻⁶³ Therefore, it can be inferred that the preference of our catalysts for methanol is due mainly to the presence of a uniform Cu-N_x structure.

Fig. 7 - ECSA of CTF-SACs. (a) Pseudocapacitance of CTF-900, CTF-Cu-900 and CTF-Cu-N-900 at 0.25 V vs Ag/AgCl from 10 to 50 mVs⁻¹. Respective CV curves of CTF-Cu-N-900 (b), CTF-Cu-900 (c), and CTF-900 (d) in the range of non-faradaic potential ranging from 0 to 0.5 V vs Ag/AgCl.

Catalyst stability is influenced by structural modifications, variations in electrolyte pH, and the presence of solution contaminants, acting synergistically.¹⁹ To assess the stability of CTF-Cu-N-900 under CO₂RR conditions, we conducted a 20-hour test. The results showed that continuous electrolysis at -0.8 V vs. Ag/AgCl (3M) did not cause a significant change in the current density, indicating its excellent catalytic stability (Fig. 5f).

The electrical conductivity of the catalysts CTF-900, CTF-Cu-900, and CTF-Cu-N-900 was investigated by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). In contrast to CTF-Cu-900 and CTF-900, as shown in Fig. 6c, N-doped CTF-Cu-N-900 had the lowest charge transfer resistance, which is advantageous for the CO₂RR because it enhances electronic contact.

Based on the calculations performed, it can be observed that CTF-900, CTF-Cu-900, and CTF-Cu-N-900 exhibit electrochemical surface areas (ECSA) of approximately 19.2, 148.0, and 270.5 cm^2 , respectively, as depicted in Figure 6d. Also, this investigation revealed that the non-faradaic potential exhibited pseudo-capacitance values of around 0.77 m.Fcm^{-2} , 5.92 m.Fcm^{-2} , and 10.82 m.Fcm^{-2} for CTF-900, CTF-Cu-900, and CTF-Cu-N-900, respectively (see Figure 7a-d). The observed high electrochemical surface area (ECSA) of CTF-Cu-N-900 can be attributed to its hierarchical porous structure, which possesses a significant surface area and pore volume. This characteristic is likely responsible for providing more active sites for the CO_2 reduction reaction (CO_2RR). The observed results are consistent with the superior catalytic performance of CTF-Cu-N-900 in the CO_2 reduction reaction (CO_2RR) compared to other prepared catalysts. Hence, this study's observed increase in CO_2RR efficiency, particularly for the CTF-Cu-N-900 catalyst, can be attributed primarily to the synergistic impact of the highly conductive pyrolyzed CTF and N-chelating ligands. This synergy facilitates rapid intermolecular ion and charge transfer, resulting in abundant active sites for the reaction. Furthermore, incorporating PDI-derived CTF inside the carbon matrix has significantly improved its electric conductivity. This enhancement facilitates electron transmission and provides highly efficient active sites for the electrochemical reduction of carbon dioxide (CO_2RR).

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, it has been shown that a highly conductive PDI-CTF can serve as carbon support for the synthesis of Cu-SACs. With 72.6% of FE and a low overpotential (0.2 V vs. RHE), the CTF-Cu-SACs have demonstrated their efficiency as electrocatalysts for converting CO_2 into methanol. On the other hand, when the overpotential was increased from 0.2 to -0.4 V vs. RHE, CTF-Cu-SACs favored syngas (CO and H_2) generation. Moreover, at -0.4 V vs. RHE, a large amount of CO with an FE of 53.2% was produced. We also discovered that by stabilizing the Cu atom and supplying more catalytically active sites in CO_2RR , the extra N-doping to the PDI-CTF significantly influences the catalytic performance of CTF-Cu-SACs. This product generation may be primarily attributable to the abundant Cu active sites with a single atom in the carbonaceous matrix of PDI-CTF. Therefore, PDI-based CTF-Cu-SACs are a promising candidate for a heterogeneous catalyst because of their simple synthesis, superior electronic characteristics, and highly monodispersed single atoms.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

Characterizations, including BET surface analysis, Raman spectrum, XPS profile, FE-SEM, SEM-EDS, and HAAD-STEM profiles, are accessible on the ACS publication website.

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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